

APPROACHES TO THE PROCESSES OF ORGANIZING AND MANAGEMENT OF AGRO-TOURISM ACTIVITIES AND THEIR CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract: *The article examines the competitiveness of graduates in higher education institutions from a theoretical and practical point of view. In the study, the concepts of competitiveness, competitiveness of higher education and competitiveness of a graduate of a higher education institution were systematized based on the approaches of foreign and domestic scientists. At the same time, the main indicators of the higher education institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2012-2021 were analyzed and trends of change were evaluated.*

The factors influencing the level of competitiveness of the graduates of Fergana State University in the specialty they are studying were evaluated by factors combined into 4 groups based on the main parameters determining the prestige of universities.

Key words: *tourism sector, domestic tourism, agrotourism activity, rural tourism, investment mechanism, economic levers, organizational-economic mechanism.*

INTRODUCTION

In the process of large-scale structural reforms in the development of the tourism sector in our country, the regional organization of agrotourism activities, aspects related to its structure and development, which create the basis for the development of international tourism, and the management of the activities of tourist enterprises within the regional structures, in the development of the regional economy in a macroeconomic balance is important.

One of the tasks of the state in the development of regions with high tourist potential for the organization of agrotourism activities is to create conditions for more fully satisfying the needs of citizens for recreation through the development of tourism and its sectors.

Restoring the physical and spiritual health of the population by taking part in rural areas and agricultural production, this type of activity plays an important role in improving the standard and quality of life of the population, while forming the agro-tourism image of certain regions. Territorial organization and management of agrotourism activity is of primary importance in the development of the tourism sector. Geographical location of

tourist enterprises and objects engaged in agrotourism activity plays a key role in effective use of agrotourism resources available in the regions and in meeting the touristic needs of the country's population.

A broader approach to researching the problems of development and management of agrotourism activities in our country is required. The reason is that the essence, features and directions of agrotourism development have not been sufficiently disclosed even in foreign scientific literature.

When starting any research work, it is necessary to learn the meaning of the basic concepts used in a particular field. It depends on having a conceptual approach and the unity of understanding the essence of certain phenomena and processes, how clearly and clearly the researcher expresses his opinion, explains this or that fact, and how correctly his evidence is accepted by other scientists and specialists. During the implementation of this research, based on the above-mentioned points, an attempt was made to develop a more complete definition of the term "agrotourism" by studying the meaning and essence of the term "agrotourism".

The analysis of the research on the problems and prospects of the development of the service and tourism sector reveals very conflicting interpretations of certain concepts related to agrotourism and its essence by different authors. This is especially true for new areas of tourism, including agrotourism. Currently, there are relatively few scientific studies devoted to the development of agrotourism activities in our country, but there are many differences in the comparative analysis of the definitions of the main concepts given in these scientific literatures.

We will consider the main approaches to the essence of the concepts of "agritourism", "rural tourism", "agricultural tourism", "ecological tourism" and "green tourism".

It should be noted that there are several approaches to considering the essence of the above concepts. One of the most common types of tourism is rural tourism and agrotourism are the same concepts. Ecological tourism is an independent direction of tourist activity. According to another approach, agrotourism and ecological tourism are directions of rural tourism.

In the studies of N. Volodin, he considers the categories "rural tourism" and "agritourism" to be synonymous. According to him, agrotourism involves the temporary stay of tourists in rural areas for the purpose of recreation or participation in agricultural activities.

A.Barlibaev and G.Nasirov understand agrotourism as a type of activity focused on the organization of tourists' recreation in rural areas or small towns, including the provision of residential services with the possibility of labor participation in the private sector and the use of natural, cultural-historical, socio-ethnographic resources .

M.Birzhakov, L.Bitkulova, D.Panova formation of a complex of services for organizing rural tourism, active types of tourism, accommodation, food, recreation, sports activities

(hunting, fishing, acquisition of knowledge and skills specific to residents of rural areas), They consider it a special type of activity that includes organization and presentation to the end user (agro-tourist). At the same time, the authors consider the concepts of "agritourism" and "rural tourism" to be equal.

According to another approach, agrotourism and ecological tourism are directions of rural tourism. Researchers V.Chayka and A.Isaev consider rural tourism as a branch of the tourism industry that uses the natural, cultural, historical, social and other resources of rural areas to create a complex tourist product.

At the same time, these authors state that agrotourism includes all types of recreational activities in rural areas (ecological tourism, agricultural tourism, sports tourism, pilgrimage, etc.). The main criterion for classifying a certain type as rural tourism, these authors define overnight accommodation for tourists in rural areas, including small towns without industrial and high-rise buildings.

According to them, agritourism implies contact with agricultural production, for example, gardening, animal husbandry, farming, etc. This approach distinguishes the directions of tourist activity in rural areas depending on the purpose and content of trips, as well as the motivation of tourists.

There are other approaches to the ratio of rural tourism, agrotourism and ecotourism. According to the approach of Z.Kamilova and S.Laipanov, agrotourism is a direction of ecological tourism, which provides recreation for people on the basis of farm or household. At the same time, these authors consider ecological tourism as a type of tourism based on contact with nature, which does not harm natural complexes, helps to protect the environment and contributes to the improvement of the well-being of local residents.

According to the socio-ecological dictionary, ecological tourism means tourism as a means of getting to know nature and regaining strength in contact with nature. When ecological tourism becomes a mass type, it can act as a means of nature protection or as a factor of its degradation.

The following definition of ecotourism is given in the studies of V. Senin: "Ecotourism is a type of tourism, the main purpose of which is to travel to ecologically clean natural areas."

The International Union for Conservation of Nature defines ecotourism as "...relatively undisturbed natural areas that promote conservation, have a 'soft' impact on the environment, provide active socio-economic participation of local residents, and explore and enjoy natural and cultural attractions." travel with responsibility to the environment", he believes.

Thus, in accordance with the approaches presented in the opinion, ecological tourism has characteristic features as a direction of tourist activity and serves in the following directions:

- preservation of natural and historical-cultural heritage;

- joint use of socio-economic benefits with the local population;
- increase the level of ecological and cultural knowledge of tourists;
- minimization of the impact of tourism activities on the environment, etc.

Application of the concept of "green tourism" implies the use of ecological methods and technologies in the field of tourism. Green tourism is considered by some authors as a socially responsible tourism that is concerned with the cultural well-being of tourist regions, the increasing use of their resources, and the minimization of environmental damage, and is interpreted as synonymous with ecotourism.

A.Yu. Aleksandrova distinguishes such concepts as "tourism in rural areas" and "rural tourism". According to his approach, the term rural tourism in the broadest sense includes all types of tourist activities carried out in rural areas. The main criterion for inclusion in this category is the territorial location symbol. At the same time, the main indicators that are the basis for classifying a certain area as a village are the population density, the size of settlements, the degree of sparseness of settlements, the structure of population employment, the leading directions of economic activity, the lifestyle of the population, etc.

A. Yu. Aleksandrova defines rural tourism as "... rural tourism is a special type of tourism that combines organized and unorganized recreation standards of tourists in rural areas in order to familiarize them with nature, rural lifestyle, farming traditions." is given.

Analyzing the phrase "rural tourism", it can be concluded that all types related to the temporary stay of tourists in rural areas belong to this type of tourism. In the dictionary compiled by S.I. Ojegov, the word "rural" means "related to life and activity outside cities and villages". In turn, the word "agrarian", in this dictionary, means "related to the use of land" and defines the criterion of this type of activity. Therefore, agrotourism implies not only a temporary stay in rural areas, but also participation in agricultural work.

Summarizing the approaches considered above, agrotourism can be defined as follows: "... agrotourism is a temporary stay of tourists in rural areas for the purpose of recreation, participation in agricultural work, contact with nature, familiarization with natural, historical and cultural areas. direction of tourist activity".

in our opinion, agrotourism is a direction of rural tourism, which is related to the stay of tourists in rural areas for the purpose of recreation, and includes the participation of vacationers in agricultural work and their acquaintance with the culture and life of the villagers.

According to our approach, ecological or "green tourism" is a direction of rural tourism that attracts tourists to travel outside urban settlements for recreation, contact with nature, environmental education and training.

Thus, at present, there is no single approach to determine the essence of rural tourism as a direction of tourist activity, due to the insufficient development of this issue in scientific research, as well as the absence of a law on rural tourism at the macro and regional level. At the same time, the development of rural tourism not only requires

favorable changes in the economy of modern villages, but also contributes to the preservation and increase of its cultural wealth and historical heritage.

Summarizing these approaches, rural tourism is an independent direction of tourist activity, including agricultural, ecological (green tourism) and other types of tourism carried out in rural areas.

The processes related to the organization and management of agrotourism activities have been studied by various researchers and scientists, and different approaches to the processes of organization and management of activities have been formed.

The forms of agrotourism activity, the complexity and versatility of its organization are reflected in the management and efficiency of management. In approaches to agrotourism activity and its components, some researchers paid special attention to the integrity of the territory where tourist service enterprises are located, while some researchers attached importance to the connection of tourist resources with the territory.

The fact that the management of agrotourism activity is organized by enterprises belonging to a number of industries and branches located within a single territory and focusing their activities on a single goal shows the need to organize the management process on the basis of a systematic approach.

In the conditions of the modern economy, specialists at any level of management are required to have a broad level of knowledge in the field of management, which forms a strategic content. No individual, enterprise, or even a whole segment of the national economy taken separately has enough opportunities to find and implement a development path that corresponds to the scale of the existing global problems. The analysis of management theory and practice of various economic entities allows establishing the need to apply the following basic scientific approach to management processes.

The main views of methodological approaches to management processes:

Approaches. Content of approaches

Administrative approach. In the administrative approach, the functions, rights, obligations and elements of the management system are regulated by means of regulatory documents.

Iterative manufacturing approach. The iterative manufacturing approach is aimed at constantly renewing the production of goods in order to meet the needs of the market at the lowest possible cost.

A dynamic approach. The object of control is considered in dialectical development, causality and interdependence

Integrative approach. An integrative approach establishes relationships between individual subsystems and management system elements, levels, and management entities.

A quantitative approach. The essence of the quantitative approach is the use of quantitative estimates with the help of mathematical, statistical, engineering calculations, etc

Integrated approach. The integrated approach takes into account technical, economic, social and other aspects of management

Marketing approach. The marketing approach involves directing the management subsystem towards the consumer

Normative approach. Norms in the management process are defined in the normative approach.

A behavioral approach. The behavioral approach involves helping the employee involved in the management process to realize their potential.

Process approach. In the process approach, management processes are considered as a set of interrelated functions

Systematic approach. In the systemic approach, any system is considered as a set of interrelated elements

Situational approach. The situational approach assumes that the application of different management methods in the process is determined by the specific situation.

A functional approach. In this case, a need is considered as a set of functions that need to be fulfilled.

Currently, special attention is paid to the following three approaches, which have made a significant contribution to the development of management theory and practice in tourism, including theoretical research and practical management processes:

1. The situational approach focuses on the fact that the universality of different management methods is determined by the situation, in other words, there is no single, "best" way to manage it due to the inevitability of problems that arise both in the enterprise itself and in its internal and external environment.

2. The systemic approach assumes that the enterprise is considered as a set of interrelated elements, such as personnel, structure, tasks and technology, aimed at achieving various goals in a changing external environment.

3. The process approach considers management as a continuous sequence of interrelated management functions, business processes.

In agrotourism activity, as in other areas of the service sector, management approaches that differ to a certain extent from management processes in material production and are related to a specific situation, process and system are considered more effective.

Within management doctrines, situational management theories gain significant importance. The essence of these theories is explained by the fact that the results of the same management actions in different situations can be significantly different from each other, therefore, in the implementation of all necessary management actions, such as planning, management or control, experts should proceed from the existing situation.

The concept of "situational management theory" was first used by R. Mockler, and the emergence of this concept is explained by the insufficient practical effectiveness of existing management theories.

Later, this theory was developed by a number of researchers (M. Follett, R. Stogdill, P. Drucker, J. Woodward, etc.) and Lawrence and Lorsch, Fidler, Hershey and Blanchard, House and Mitchell situational management models were created.

The main point of the situational approach is the situation, which is a set of specific circumstances that have a strong influence on the outcome of the activity at a certain time. The situational approach does not negate the concepts of traditional management theory, behavioral school, and management science school, and at the same time, it is a way of thinking about organizational problems and their solutions, like the systemic approach of management.

The following basic management principles apply in the situational approach to management processes in agrotourism activities, which are considered a component of socio-economic systems:

1. The principle of correct interpretation of the situation.
2. The principle of using management methods and methods that have shown their effectiveness based on the specific characteristics of a specific situation.
3. The principle of foreseeing possible positive and negative consequences of using a specific method or concept.

Although the situational approach to management processes has practical advantages, some researchers criticize the situational approach based on insufficient theoretical basis, lack of general laws for specific situations, insufficient predictive ability and initiative.

Another approach to the management of agrotourism activity is the systematic approach, and this approach reveals and clarifies the principle of systematic management.

The founder of the systematic approach to management processes in the West is Ludwig von Bertalanffy. The "general theory of systems" created by L. Bertalanfi is the basis of the systematic approach to management processes.

The main task of the concept of the systemic approach is to find a set of laws and principles that explain the behavior, activity and development of various systems, based on the understanding of the system as a set of interrelated elements (parts). The system concept is a set of approaches and methods to the organization and management of system analysis and synthesis, in which the central place is occupied by the concept of the system.

An open system includes factors from the surrounding environment, such as information, energy, materials, capital and human resources, that enter into the activity of the enterprise. In the process of transformation of factors, the company processes these factors, turns them into products or services, which are the results of the company's activities that are released to the external environment. If the activity of the enterprise is effective, additional value is created in the process of processing the incoming factors, as a result of which other results such as increase in profit, market share and sales volume,

implementation of the function of social responsibility, satisfaction of material and moral needs of employees, and development of the enterprise occur.

The management system is regulated by means of feedback between the management object and the subject within the system, that is, appropriate changes are made. The system approach often uses the concept of subsystems that make up the system. Although subsystems are considered parts of integrated complex systems, in many cases they are separate systems themselves.

A number of researchers explain that the advantages of a systematic approach in systems research open up the following opportunities:

reveals the essence of the process as a set of components connected by a single logic and common direction;

- organization of the perception of a complex set of vertical and horizontal relationships of elements within the studied system;

- allows to qualitatively reveal the essence of the integrity of the system as a whole unit.

Taking into account these circumstances, it is important to determine the sequence of operations to achieve the goals of the lower level in the strategy and tactics of the operation. For this, a systematic approach in the form of a "tree of goals" is recommended as the most optimal methodological basis for the logical structure of activities, the ordering of goals in the context of complex relationships, and the clarification of problems. It is known that the goal tree allows to reduce the path to the final goal and on this basis individual tasks.

Another approach that is widely used in the management of agrotourism activities is the process approach, which looks at management processes in the form of interrelated activities or functions.

Based on the views of A. Fayol as a basis for the process approach, a number of researchers put the process approach in the form of a theory. Most representatives of this approach emphasize that the final result of management processes is reflected as management in action.

In the process approach, the management process is presented as a system of sequential and parallel interconnected planning-organization-motivation-control functions, in addition, communication and decision-making processes are connected to the management process. In other words, communication and decision-making are carried out concurrently with successively related management functions.

The possibility of measuring the changes occurring in the processes of agrotourism development is provided in the system of criteria and indicators based on the principles and methods describing public events and quantities, taking into account the following situations:

determining the development trends and current situation of agrotourism;

- studying the directions and characteristics of agrotourism flows;

- distinguishing and evaluating its quantitative and qualitative characteristics in the development of agrotourism.

The researches of M.B.Birzhakov and I.S.Kabirov occupy a special place among approaches to the processes of organization and management of agrotourism activities. Because in these studies, the formation and development stages of the tourist product were deeply studied, the conditions for organizing tours were systematized, and at the same time, the geography of agrotourism activity was analyzed.

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